

Original Research Article

Public Awareness of Stroke among Adult People in Eastern Region of Saudi Arabia, Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

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Stroke is a serious health problem worldwide, which has been classified as the second leading cause of death. Around 15 million people are experiencing stroke each year and 5 million of them go dead. The Saudi Arabia mortality rate related to stroke was 6.4%. The aim of this study is to measure awareness and perception of stroke among adult people in Al-Ahsa city, Eastern Region, of Saudi Arabia. Data collected from participants through distributing an electronic self-structured questionnaire. This mobile application survey was carried out between May 20 to 31, 2020 in Al-Ahsa city of Saudi Arabia regarding stroke knowledge. The sample of overall community was 1406 (37.6% males and 62.4% females). Our results showed that (76.6%) of the participants had poor general knowledge about stroke. Roughly (74%) were aware that the altered body organ was the brain. Around (53.3%) would seek emergency medical care in case of stroke. Stroke is a worldwide health challenge, along with increasing records of mortalities and stroke-associated disability in current years. Our results showed that the majority of the participants had poor general knowledge about stroke. Near to half of participants had not knowledge about signs and symptoms of stroke.

Keywords: Awareness, Perception, Stroke, Saudi Arabia

INTRODUCTION

There are many neurological disorders. Stroke is considered the most serious one which becomes the second leading causes of death. It attacks the brain and impairs its functions by cutting off the blood supply from a certain part of the brain. It happens suddenly and affects the body parts that controlled by affected part of the brain (Robert and Zamzami, 2014).

From all neurological disorders, stroke is the tremendously avoidable one. Several risk factors of stroke, involving hypertension, high cholesterol, diabetes, heart disease and smoking can be avoided via more healthy daily life choices or by medicine. Better considerate of risk factors and alert signs for stroke would accelerate health interventions directed to lowering disabilities from stroke (Collins et al., 2002).

In Saudi Arabia, stroke is growing rapidly and causing death for high risk people. The estimated rate of stroke incidence in Saudi Arabia was 29.8 per 100,000 per year (Alzahrani et al., 2019). There are different studies confirmed that there is a relationship between community awareness of stroke and the incidence of it. People who are at highest risk to get stroke have the poorest knowledge about it (Robert and Zamzami, 2014). In addition, there are many studies emphasis that there is a big deficit in level of stroke awareness and knowledge in the Saudi population (Alhazzani et al., 2019). A survey conducted about the ten most common causes of death in Saudi Arabia in 2017, added stroke in this top ten causes and reported that the mortality rate due to stroke was (6.4%) (Institute for Health Metrics

and Evaluation, 2017).

There are different types of stroke. However, the most common type is ischemic stroke which happens when an artery in the brain is blocked by embolism or thrombus. Hemorrhagic stroke is another type of stroke which happens when an artery in the brain is exploded (Hosseininezhad et al., 2017). There are many risk factors which make people at risk to get stroke in their life. Some of these risk factors are modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. Stroke awareness about alert signs and risk factors seem to be low in all populations (Nicol and Thrift, 2005). In addition, World Health Organization (WHO) considers obesity and smoking as risk factors of stroke. The common risk factors that present in Saudi population are hypertension, heart diseases, diabetes mellitus and smoking (Alzahrani et al., 2019).

Across the years, the stroke frequency in poor and medium countries has further than doubled over. Throughout these periods stroke incidence has reduced in high-income countries (Feigin et al., 2010). So we need to improve the public health knowledge about stroke to all people especially people who have potential stroke victims in order to reduce the number of people maybe get stroke through many ways such as social media, first aid programs or various teaching strategies like lecture (Pothiban et al., 2018).

Fast services necessitate that there is awareness about the alerting signs of stroke. Understanding of risk factors and warning signs in the common population has constantly been observed to be inadequate, with knowledge levels worst in groups that have the maximum risk of stroke, e.g., those aged above 75 (Schneider et al., 2003; Carroll et al., 2004; Reeves et al., 2008).

Aim of the study

This study aimed to measure awareness and perception of stroke among adult people in Al-Ahsa city of Saudi Arabia.

METHOD

This online descriptive cross-sectional population-based survey was carried out between May 20 to 31, 2020 in Al-Ahsa city of Saudi Arabia regarding stroke awareness. Convenience sampling method used during the pandemic lockdown period. After 31st of May the end of pandemic lockdown period. The methodological procedure used in this research divided into six stages. Stage 1: questionnaire design and initial preparation. Stage 2: validity and reliability and pilot study. Stage 3: final survey design and sample selection. Stage 4: data collection through WhatsApp. Stage 5: data coding,

data-file construction, Stage 6: analysis, and final report.

Based on Ministry of Communication and Information Technology's statistic 2020, 18.3 million Saudis are using social media in their everyday living. In the age of technology, most adult people have their own cell phone and mobile number (Ministry of Communication and Information Technology, 2020). For that, we chose WhatsApp Application to collect data. Data collected through distributing a self-structured questionnaire and sent in an electronic format via WhatsApp Application to the participants. Based on Municipality, the total population of Al-Ahsa city is 1.3 million (Al Ahsa Chamber, 2019). The inclusion criteria were people who aged more than 18-year-old, lived in Al-Ahsa, and used WhatsApp Application. The form was disseminated between the participants via the WhatsApp groups. The survey was anonymous. The data of the survey were collected and analyzed using the online website Google form. The finalization of the form was thought to be informed consent to take part in the study, The questionnaire was accessible via the coming link (<https://ddei3-0-ctp.trendmicro.com>).

A 27-items questionnaire was created after a wide-ranging literature review. It was also modified from alike studies. Additionally, the questionnaire was converted into Arabic, the native language. The questionnaire was validated by 2 experts who approved the suggested questionnaire. The researchers conducted a pilot study on 30 participants to assess the simplicity and understanding of the questionnaire and to investigate the reliability of the questionnaire also. The uncertain points were excluded, and the questionnaire was processed depending on the findings of the trial run analyzation.

The study questionnaire contained two sections. The first section consists of demographic data, which is a general information of each participant. The second section consists of close-end questions which assessed the participant's awareness about stroke. These questions focused on general information about stroke, risk factors, signs and symptoms, treatment, and prevention. Three-point Likert scale which consist of choices of "right", "wrong", and "I don't know" is used. The replies were given one point for the accurate answer and zero point for the wrong or uncertain reply.

Generally, the knowledge part of the questionnaire consisted of 18 questions and in case the participants finished the complete questions accurately, 18 counting points were given as one point for one correct answer. Those participants who achieved knowledge score higher than 15 (85%) were judged as V. Good level, while the scores between 11 and 15 (60-< 85%) were considered as Good level. The score below 11 (< 60%) were considered as Poor level. The data were recorded and interpreted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 23.0).

The study was approved by the research and ethical

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Demographic data	N=1406	%
Age:		
18-24	385	(27.4%)
25-39	391	(27.8%)
40-59	568	(40.4%)
60-79	62	(4.4%)
80 or older	0	(0%)
Gender:		
Male	528	(37.6%)
Female	878	(62.4%)
MaritalStatus:		
Single	410	(29.2%)
Married	940	(66.9%)
Divorced	38	(2.7%)
Widow	18	(1.3%)
Education level:		
Illiterate/unlearned	2	(0.1%)
Primary school	12	(0.9%)
Secondary school	61	(4.3%)
High school	317	(22.5%)
University or above	1014	(72.1%)
Occupation:		
Student	332	(23.6%)
Employed	623	(44.3%)
Un employed	310	(22%)
Retired	141	(10%)
Income:		
High	127	(9%)
Middle	1050	(74.7%)
Low	229	(16.3%)
Do you have medical history?		
Diabetes mellitus	60	(4.3%)
Hypertension	89	(6.3%)
Heart disease	7	(0.5%)
Obesity	84	(6%)
Smoking	32	(2.3%)
Other diseases	169	(12%)
I don't have any health problem	787	(56%)
More than one disease	173	(12.3%)

committee of the College of Applied Medical Sciences of King Faisal University.

RESULTS

Table (1) shows socio-demographic characteristics of participants. The present study sample covered 1406 of adult people. It is found that near to half 568 (40.4%) of the participant's age was from forty to fifty- nine. Also, two third of participants 940 (66.9%) were married. The education level of most participants 1014 (72.1%) was university degree or above and 623 (44.3%) of them were employed. Furthermore, it is observed that 1050 (74.7%) of the participant's income was middle income. More than half 787 (56%) of participants had no health problem, while 173 (12.3%) had more than one disease.

Table (2) illustrates the percentages distribution of participants' knowledge about stroke attack. It was found that the majority of the participants 935 (66.5 %) heard or read about stroke and 418 (44.7%) of them read in social media or book while 380 (40.6%) heard from doctor. Also, 1040 (74%) of the participants were defined the stroke as lack of blood supply to brain. In addition, more than half of the participants 766 (54.5%) didn't know types of stroke. It was noticed that 1001(71.2%) of the participants reported stroke as a medical emergency and almost one fifth of them didn't know.

Table (3) presents the percentages distribution of participants' knowledge about risk factors and clinical manifestation of stroke. It was found that the participants didn't know if family history can cause stroke or if it increases in people under the "age of 65" 670 (47.7%) and 678(48.2%) respectively. However, most of the

Table 2. Participants' Knowledge about Stroke Attack (Awareness of subjects about stroke attack)

General Information about Stroke	N=1406	%
Did you hear or read about stroke?		
Yes	935	(66.5%)
No	343	(24.4%)
I don't know	128	(9.1%)
If "Yes". What is the source from which you obtained this information?		
N= 935		
I read about it in social media, books and internet	418	(44.7%)
I heard about it from doctor	380	(40.6%)
I know a person who has stroke	94	(10.1%)
I don't remember	43	(4.6%)
Is stroke due to lack of blood supply to brain?		
True	1040	(74 %)
False	63	(4.5%)
I don't know	303	(21.6%)
The most common type of stroke is ischemic stroke?		
True	543	(38.6%)
False	97	(6.9%)
I don't know	766	(54.5%)
Stroke is a medical emergency?		
True	1001	(71.2%)
False	109	(7.8%)
I don't know	296	(21.1%)

Table 3. Participants' Knowledge about Risk Factors and Clinical Manifestation of Stroke

Risk Factors of Stroke	N=1406	%
Family history can cause stroke.		
True	416	(29.6%)
False	320	(22.8%)
I don't know	670	(47.7%)
The incidence of stroke increases mostly in people under the age of 65.		
True	205	(14.6%)
False	523	(37.2%)
I don't know	678	(48.2%)
Diabetes increases the incidence of having stroke		
True	515	(36.6%)
False	161	(11.5%)
I don't know	730	(51.9%)
High blood pressure increases the incidence of having stroke		
True	872	(62%)
False	46	(3.3%)
I don't know	488	(34.7%)
High level of Cholesterol increases the incidence of having stroke		
True	755	(53.7%)
False	64	(4.6%)
I don't know	587	(41.7%)
Epilepsy increases the incidence of having stroke		
True	433	(30.8%)
False	133	(9.5%)
I don't know	840	(59.7%)
Signs and Symptoms of Stroke		
The symptoms of stroke usually appear		
Gradually	256	(18.2%)
Suddenly	753	(53.6%)
I don't know	397	(28.2%)
Slurred speech can be recognized as a sign of stroke		
True	689	(49%)
False	153	(10.9%)
I don't know	564	(40.1%)

Table 3. Continue

Weakness in arms and legs can be recognized as a sign of stroke		
True	653	(46.4%)
False	98	(7%)
I don't know	655	(46.6%)
Stroke usually affects		
The right side of the body only	85	(6%)
The left side of the body only	161	(11.5%)
One side of the body (Right side or left side)	727	(51.7%)
Both sides of the body at the same time	433	(30.8%)

Table 4. Participants' Knowledge about Treatment and Prevention of stroke

Treatment	N=1406	%
Is there any current treatment for stroke?		
Yes, there is	428	(30.4%)
No, there isn't	257	(18.3%)
I don't know	721	(51.3%)
Nobody makes a full recovery after a stroke.		
True	589	(41.9%)
False	217	(15.4%)
I don't know	600	(42.7%)
Prevention		
Which of these could help reduce the chance of stroke?		
Fresh air	75	(5.3%)
Vitamin C	26	(1.8%)
Exercise and healthy lifestyle	939	(66.8%)
I don't know	366	(26%)

Table 5. Participants' Response in Case of stroke attack

Response	N=1406	%
What should you do if you see a patient just getting attack?		
Advise him to take rest	45	(3.2%)
Get him to a local hospital	611	(43.5%)
Call 997	750	(53.3%)

Table 6. Total knowledge score about stroke

	Frequency	Percent	Mean and Std. Dev
Very good	0	0	7.61 ± 3.496
Good	329	23.4	Range 1-15/18
Poor	1077	76.6	

participant's answered that diabetes 515 (36.6%), high blood pressure 872 (62%) and high cholesterol 755 (53.7%) and epilepsy 433 (30.8%) were the risk factors. Also, it was found that more than half of the participants answered the stroke usually appears suddenly and affects one side of the body (Right side or left side) 753(53.6%) and 727 (51.7%) respectively. Also nearly half reported "Slurred speech and weakness in arms and legs can be recognized as a sign of stroke 689 (49%) and 653 (46.4%) respectively.

Table (4) illustrates the percentages distribution of participants' knowledge about treatment of stroke. It was

found that more than half of participants 721(51.3%) were uncertain if there is a treatment or not. It was found that the answer nobody makes a full recovery after a stroke stated by 589(41.9%). Also, it was observed that more than two thirds of the participants 939 (66.8%) stated that practicing exercise and healthy lifestyle will reduce chance of stroke.

Table (5) shows percentages distribution of participants' response about attack of stroke. It was observed that more than half of participants 750 (53.3%) will call 997 if they see a person has stroke attack.

Table (6) represents the total score of participant's

Table 7. Relationship between Participant's Socio-Demographic Data and their Total Knowledge Score

	Poor	Good	Sign.
Age			
18-24	284	101	.717
25-39	319	72	
40-59	434	134	
60-79	40	22	
Total	1077	329	
Sex			
Male	663	215	.214
Female	414	114	
Total	1077	329	
Education level			
Illiterate/unlearned	2	0	.004*
Primary school	11	1	
Secondary school	50	11	
High school	257	60	
University or above	757	257	
Total	1077	329	
Income			
High	79	48	.001*
Middle	179	50	
Low	819	231	
Total	1077	329	
Medical history			
Diabetes mellitus	44	16	.000*
Hypertension	68	21	
Heart disease	4	3	
Obesity	69	15	
Smoking	24	8	
Other diseases	126	43	
I don't have any health problem	611	176	
More than one answer	102	76	

*P- Value Significant at < .001-.005

knowledge about stroke which is 1-15 out of 18 and mean (7.61± 3.496). It was observed that most of them have poor knowledge about stroke 1077 (76.6%).

Table (7) illustrates the relationship between participant's socio-demographic data and their total score of knowledge about stroke attack. Statistically significant difference was found between participant's educational level, income and medical history and their total score of knowledge (P-value = .004*, .001*, .000* respectively). No statistically significant differences were illustrated between participant's age and sex and their total score of knowledge.

DISCUSSION

In attempt to measure the level of awareness of adult people in Al-Ahsa city about stroke, a self-structured questionnaire was administered. Our results showed that (76.6%) of the participants had poor general knowledge about stroke. Based on Alzahrani findings of their study that was conducted in Tabuk city of Saudi Arabia, the knowledge of stroke was poor (Alzahrani et al., 2019). In

consistent with the results another study done in Eastern Region of Saudi Arabia to measure the knowledge of high school girls about stroke, the study showed that high school student's knowledge about stroke was low, as (91.1%) of participants had a low-level knowledge score (Alsubaie et al., 2020). And another study conducted in Ireland by Hickey A, found that there was a significant gap in awareness in relation to stroke between old population. These studies findings were compatible with our findings (Hickey et al., 2009).

Our study revealed that, (74 %) of participants defined stroke correctly as lack of blood supply to brain. This is in the same line with a study of Alhazzani F, which conducted in Abha city of Saudi Arabia which showed that (87.3%) of participants defined stroke correctly (Alzahrani et al., 2019).

In our study, (36.6%) of participants identified the diabetes as a risk factor of stroke, while (62%) of them identified hypertension as a risk factor of stroke and (53.7%) of them identified hypercholesterolemia as a risk factor of stroke. On the other hand, these findings were in congruent with the study of Pancioli AM, who reported that hypertension was detected as highly repeated risk

factor of stroke, following it stress, hypercholesterolemia, smoking and obesity (Pancioli et al., 1998).

Our study reported that, near to half of participants had knowledge about signs and symptoms of stroke. They reported symptoms of stroke as slurred speech (49%), weakness in arms and legs (46.4%). In addition, (53.6%) of participants know that the symptoms appear suddenly and (51.7%) of them know that stroke affect right or left side of the body. However, the study of Hickey A, presented that from the list of alert signs, just one (inaudible speech) was recognized by more than half of participants (Hickey et al., 2009). These findings differs slightly with Sug Yoon study findings where disturbance of vision was discovered to be the most frequently recognized warning sign (Sug Yoon et al., 2001).

In our study, more than half of participants (51.3%) were uncertain if there is a treatment for stroke or not. In addition, practicing exercise and healthy lifestyle will contribute to reducing the chance of stroke stated by (66.8%) of participants. Our results were similarly with a study of Farrag et al. which found that the level of stroke awareness and knowledge in prevention point was that participants recognized as control of hypertension (46.7%), healthy diet(46.7%), cholesterol lowering (39.9%), diabetes control (31.7%), and smoking cessation (47.3%) (Farrag et al., 2018). Another study done by Hickey A, found that almost of all the participant had lack of ability to recognize and react to stroke warning signs (Hickey et al., 2009). In constant with the study of The European Stroke Organization who found that shortage of community awareness associated with responses to stroke attack (European Stroke Organisation (ESO) Executive Committee, 2008).

Our study discovered that, the participants' answers reflected not bad response to stroke attack. (53.3%) of participants will call emergency services. On the other hand, the study of Hatzitolios A, who found that (43.5%) of the participants replied that they would call an ambulance (Hatzitolios et al., 2014). In another study in china done by Wei Y et al, who found that less than half (46.6%) in northwest decided to call emergency service rapidly (Wei et al., 2018).

Our study confirmed that there was statistically significant difference between participant's educational level, income and medical history and their total score of knowledge. Study of Li S, presented diverse significantly relation between oldness, gender, area, socioeconomic level, and stroke risk (Li et al., 2019).

Our study showed that the correlation between knowledge and age was insignificant. It was in constant with the study of Hickey A, who found that individuals in younger age groups have been indicated to be had more knowledge than older individuals (Hickey et al., 2009). Another study done by Sadighi A, who found that younger age and a high level of education is significantly associated with a higher rate of identifying stroke

(Sadighi et al., 2018). These results were in consistent with study of Li S, who found that older age was associated with more awareness (Li et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

Stroke is a worldwide health challenge, along with increasing records of mortalities and stroke-associated disability in current years. Our results showed that the majority of the participants had poor general knowledge about stroke. Near to half of participants had not knowledge about signs and symptoms of stroke.

Conflicts of interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability: The data are available with the corresponding author upon request.

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